

TEACHERS' STRATEGIES IN REMEDIATING THE LEAST MASTERED COMPETENCIES IN MATHEMATICS 7 TOWARDS THE DEVELOPMENT OF LM-BASED LESSON EXEMPLARS

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the teachers strategies in remediating the least mastered competencies in Mathematics 7 towards the remediation of LM-based Lesson exemplars. This study employed the descriptive-correlational design of research. Respondents were 24 Mathematics 7 teachers and 274 students from the public junior high schools in the division of Marinduque. Through survey questionnaire, data on teacher demographics, strategies, students' motivation, study habits and academic performance were collected and analyzed. Results revealed that collaborative learning, explicit instruction, differentiated instruction, and repetition were commonly utilized strategies, while game-based instruction and the use of models and manipulatives were less frequent. Despite diverse motivations and study habits among students, their overall academic performance was satisfactory. Findings revealed that educational attainment has a significant difference on teachers' strategies. However, statistical analysis indicated that teacher strategies had no significant relationship with student study habits, motivation, or academic performance. The output of this study is least mastered competencies-based lesson exemplars integrating teachers' strategies.

Keywords: *Teachers Strategies, Least Mastered Competencies, Motivation, Study Habits, Academic Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Mathematics is an important subject taught at all levels of education. Unexpectedly, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated the current education crisis and widened the math skills gap among young students (Sooknanan & Seemungal, 2023). As evidenced by the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), the Philippines ranks low in mathematics, with only 16% of students achieving at least a proficiency level 2. Furthermore, the majority of Filipino students struggle with foundational math concepts, indicating a significant need for remediation and support (SEAMEO INNOTECH, 2022).

Murillo & Tan's (2022) recent study highlights specific competencies, such as set operations and number line concepts, as areas requiring targeted intervention programs. To address these challenges, the Department of Education (DepEd) initiated the MATATAG: Bansang Makabata, Batang Makabansa program, aiming to restore mathematics learning amidst the pandemic-induced disruptions. Additionally, the National Learning Camp (NLC) was launched to enhance student performance and teacher capacity, prioritizing student well-being, inclusive education, and positive learning environments (DepEd, 2023). The DepEd's Classroom Assessment Policy Guidelines emphasize educational interventions for students scoring below 75 in any subject, emphasizing the importance of preventing learning loss and ensuring no student is left behind (Department Order No. 08 s. 2015).

Shimazoe and Aldrich (2018) highlight the benefits of cooperative learning, emphasizing its positive impact on deep learning, academic performance, social skills, and critical thinking abilities. Similarly, Jitendra et al. (2015) conducted a randomized controlled trial demonstrating the efficacy of explicit instruction in enhancing students' conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills in mathematics, particularly in proportional reasoning. Furthermore, recent research on differentiated instruction supports its effectiveness in addressing students' diverse learning needs and boosting confidence in fundamental mathematical operations (Aguhayon et al., 2020). Moreover, Heyd-Metzuyanim and Graven (2016) and Kim et al. (2015) emphasize the positive outcomes of peer tutoring, including improved math performance and increased motivation among students, while Hoops et al. (2016) highlight the role of peer tutoring in creating a supportive learning community focused on mastering mathematical concepts.

As a secondary school math teacher, the researcher has firsthand experience witnessing students' struggles with fundamental math concepts, exacerbated by math anxiety and negative perceptions of the subject. Given the importance of math proficiency for future academic and career success, the development of effective remedial programs is imperative. With a focus on mathematics teaching practices and achievement trends, the researcher aims to identify teacher strategies for remediating the least mastered competencies in Mathematics 7, seeking scalable solutions to address fundamental gaps (Torres, 2021). The researcher is primarily interested in identifying the teacher strategies for remediating the least mastered competencies in Mathematics 7.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to determine the strategies of Grade 7 Mathematics teachers in remediating the least mastered competencies in selected schools in the division of Marinduque towards developing a Mathematics learning package. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Employment Status
 - 1.4 Educational Attainment
 - 1.5 Length of Service
 - 1.6 Number of Trainings Attended Related to Mathematics
 - 1.7. Average number of hours per training
2. What strategies do the teachers employ in remediating the least mastered competencies in Mathematics 7?
3. Is there a significant difference in the strategies employed by the teacher respondents in remediating the least mastered competencies in Mathematics 7 when grouped according to profile?
4. What are the students' motivational orientations, study habits, and academic performance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between:
 - 5.1. teachers' strategies and students' motivation
 - 5.2. teachers' strategies and study habits
 - 5.3. teachers' strategies and academic performance
6. What Least Mastered-Based Lesson Exemplar can be crafted based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to explore the relationships between teaching strategies of Grade 7 Mathematics teachers and their impact on student motivation, study habits, and academic performance. Conducted in Marinduque, Philippines, the study sampled 24 teachers and 274 students from 17 public junior high schools using cluster random sampling for teachers and stratified simple random sampling for students. Data were gathered through two questionnaires, one developed by the researcher and another adapted from the MSLQ by Pintrich et al.(1993). Validity was ensured through expert feedback, leading to enhancements in the questionnaires. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, t-tests, and Spearman Rank Correlation to assess relationships and differences among variables.

RESULTS

I. Demographic Profile of the Teacher-Respondents

The tables below present the demographic profile in terms of age, sex, length of service, employment status, number of training/seminars attended related to Mathematics, the average number of hours per training and educational attainment.

Table 1

Profile distribution of the respondents

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
25 years and below	4	16.7
26-30 years old	5	20.8
31-35 years old	1	4.2
36-40 years old	3	12.5
41-45 years old	3	12.5
46-50 years old	2	8.3
51-55 years old	3	12.5
56-60 years old	2	8.3
above 61 years old	1	4.2
Total	24	100.0
Sex		
Male	8	33.3
Female	16	66.7
Total	24	100.0
Total Number of Years in Teaching		
0-5 years	5	20.8
6-10 years	8	33.3
More than 10 years	11	45.8
Total	24	100.0
Employment Status		
Regular	23	95.8
Substitute	1	4.2
Total	24	100.0
Number of Trainings/Seminars Attended Related to Mathematics		
1 Training	7	29.2
2 Trainings	1	4.2
3 Trainings	1	4.2
4 trainings	2	8.3
8 Trainings	2	8.3
9 Trainings	1	4.2
10 Trainings	1	4.2
No Training	9	37.5
Total	24	100.0
Average Number of hours per Training		
8 hours	3	12.5
16 hours	1	4.2
24 hours	9	37.5
32 hours	2	8.3
No Training	9	37.5

Total	24	100.0
Education Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree Holder	3	12.5
With units in master's degree	20	83.3
Master's Degree	1	4.2
Total	24	100.0

II. Strategies of the Teacher-Respondents

Table 2

Strategies employed by the respondents to remediate the least mastered competencies in mathematics

Strategies	5	4	3	2	1	Mean	SD	DI
Differentiated Instruction	9	8	7	0	0	4.08	0.830	Always
Game-Based Instruction	3	7	8	6	0	3.29	0.999	Sometimes
Explicit Instruction	11	9	3	1	0	4.25	0.847	Always
Use of Models and Manipulatives	3	6	12	3	0	3.38	0.875	Sometimes
Collaborative Learning	13	7	4	0	0	4.38	0.770	Always
Peer Teaching	8	10	5	0	1	4.00	0.978	Often
Repetition	12	6	2	4	0	4.08	1.139	Always
Use of Visual Representations	9	14	1	0	0	4.33	0.565	Often

Table 2 presents the strategies teachers use in teaching mathematics. As observed, Collaborative learning has the highest mean of 4.38, interpreted as "Always". Explicit instruction (4.25), Differentiated Instruction (4.08), and Repetition (4.08) also appeared to be always used by the teachers. This inclination may stem from their perceived effectiveness in promoting student engagement, facilitating learning, and aligning with curriculum standards. Conversely, game-based instruction (3.29) and the use of models and manipulatives (3.38), while recognized as valuable, are employed less frequently, possibly due to perceived challenges in implementation, resource limitations, or concerns about their fit within existing instructional frameworks.

III. Test of Significant Difference Between Teachers' Profile and Strategies

Table 3

Statistical table showing the significant difference between the strategies employed by the teacher respondents according to profile variables

Grouping Variable	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
Age	0.313	Not significant	Ho not rejected
Sex	0.928	Not significant	Ho not rejected
Educational Attainment	0.022	Significant	Ho is rejected
Employment Status	0.108	Not significant	Ho not rejected
Number of Trainings Attended	0.091	Not significant	Ho not rejected
Number of Hours per Training	0.057	Not significant	Ho not rejected
Number of Years in Service	0.166	Not significant	Ho not rejected

Table 3 presents the statistical table displaying the difference between teachers' profiles and teacher strategies. Educational Attainment with a p-value of 0.022 appeared to have a significant difference in academic performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This result suggests that the level of education achieved by teachers may play a role in shaping their approach to instruction and the specific strategies they adopt in the classroom. Teachers with higher levels of educational attainment, such as master's degrees or specialized certifications, may be exposed to a broader range of pedagogical theories and methodologies, influencing their teaching practices.

On the other hand, other demographic profiles like age (0.313), sex (0.918), employment status (0.108), number of training attended (0.091), number of hours per training (0.057) and number of years in teaching (0.166) have p-value greater than 0.05 which indicates that there is no significant relationship; therefore the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Motivational Orientations of the Students

Table 4.1

Motivation of Students

Motivation	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	Mode	D
1. In a class like this, I prefer course material that really challenges me so I can learn new things.	50	23	22	7	5	1	3	7	VT
2. If I study in appropriate ways, then I will be able to learn materials in this course.	45	35	17	9	3	0	2	7	VT
3. When I take a test, I think about how poorly I am doing compared with other students.	11	16	20	12	11	17	23	1	VU

4. I think I will be able to use what I learn in this course in other courses.	58	20	15	12	1	3	2	7	VT
5. I believe I will receive an excellent grade in this class.	30	32	26	13	1	4	4	6	MLT
6. I'm certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in the readings for this course.	14	29	28	20	8	5	7	6	MLT
7. Getting a good grade in this class is the most satisfying thing for me right now.	69	11	18	2	4	3	4	7	VT
8. When I take a test, I think about items on other parts of the test I can't answer.	37	23	21	19	8	1	2	7	VT
9. It is my own fault if I don't learn the materials in this course.	40	22	23	9	9	4	4	7	VT
10. It is important for me to learn the course material in this course.	68	26	12	2	2	0	1	7	VT
11. The most important thing for me right now is improving my overall grade point average, so my main concern in this class is getting a good grade.	66	17	13	8	2	0	4	7	VT
12. I'm confident I can learn the basic concepts taught in this course.	51	21	17	12	2	4	4	7	VT
13. If I can, I want to get better grades in this class than most of other students.	40	37	14	8	8	3	1	7	VT
14. When I take a test, I think of consequences of failing.	31	24	25	12	6	9	4	7	VT
15. I'm confident I can understand the most complex material presented by the instructor in this course.	25	34	32	13	4	1	2	6	MLT
16. In a class like this, I prefer course material that arouses my curiosity, even if it is difficult to learn.	43	22	23	14	4	4	1	7	VT
17. I am very interested in the content area of this course.	55	28	12	12	2	2	0	7	VT
18. If I try hard enough, then I will understand the course material.	54	21	22	7	3	3	1	7	VT
19. I have an uneasy, upset feeling when I take an exam.	29	23	20	15	11	8	5	7	VT
20. I'm confident I can do an excellent job on the assignment and test in this course.	41	27	21	12	6	2	2	7	VT
21. I expect to do well in this class.	39	31	18	11	6	2	4	7	VT
22. The most satisfying thing for me in this course is trying to understand the content as thoroughly as possible.	57	18	24	7	2	3	0	7	VT
23. I think the course material in this class is useful for me to learn.	61	23	15	5	4	2	0	7	VT
24. When I have the opportunity in this class, I choose course assignment that I can learn from even if they don't guarantee a good grade.	41	28	25	11	3	2	1	7	VT
25. If I don't understand the course material, it is because I didn't try hard enough.	34	20	24	23	3	5	2	7	VT

26. I like the subject matter of the course.	46	34	18	8	2	2	1	7	VT
27. Understanding the subject matter if this course.	63	22	14	8	3	0	0	7	VT
28. I feel my heart beating fast when I take an exam.	39	29	21	10	7	3	1	7	VT
29. I'm certain I can master the skill being taught in this class.	20	31	30	19	7	3	0	6	MLT
30. I want to do well in this class because it is important to show my ability to my family, friends, employer, or others.	58	26	12	9	0	3	2	7	VT
31. Considering the difficult of this course, the teacher, and my skills, I think I will do well in this course.	56	29	14	8	3	1	0	7	VT
Mode								7	VT

IV. Study Habits of the Students

Table 4.2

Study Habits of Students

Study Habits	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	Mode	D
1. I have trouble finishing test on time.	16	24	25	16	13	6	12	5	T
2. I set aside a regular time for studying every day.	31	22	26	17	10	4	2	7	VT
3. I gave up if an assignment is difficult.	12	14	12	14	19	16	25	3	SU
4. I have difficult determining important points in lecture	17	20	28	20	12	10	5	5	T
5. Before class starts, I review yesterday's lecture notes	23	28	27	17	7	3	7	6	MLT
6. I waste time because I am not organized.	4	16	24	15	12	19	23	5	T
7. I focus entirely on my work when I study.	37	29	18	14	7	2	5	7	VT
8. I don't bother taking notes on lecture.	9	19	16	12	15	22	18	2	U
9. I get sleepy when I study.	20	10	16	15	11	8	30	1	VU
10. I enjoy learning.	59	26	16	5	0	3	3	7	VT
11. Before answering an essay question, I organize what I am going to write.	42	24	20	19	7	0	0	7	VT
12. I have difficulty concentrating when I study.	12	33	28	14	4	16	5	6	MLT
13. I could get better grades.	37	33	20	12	4	3	3	7	VT
14. I try to record everything a teacher says in a lecture.	30	29	18	10	11	6	9	7	VT
15. I'd rather get through fast than have a perfect paper.	12	7	24	15	18	14	22	5	T
16. I usually seek a quiet place to study.	41	27	19	11	5	5	4	7	VT

17. Before I leave class, I make sure that I know what homework to do and how to do it.	42	24	17	12	8	5	4	7	VT
18. I have a hard time getting interested in some of my subjects.	19	23	22	16	11	7	14	6	MLT
19. Good grades are important to me.	67	14	9	13	6	1	1	7	VT
20. I know what time of the day I do my best studying.	32	31	23	14	2	3	7	7	VT
21. I study only when I feel like it.	16	14	17	18	14	14	19	1	VU
22. I often have trouble finding time to study.	14	19	23	20	10	16	10	5	T
23. I remember little of what I study.	24	16	18	21	12	10	11	7	VT
24. Test make me nervous that I can't do my best.	24	16	12	15	12	19	14	7	VT
25. I wait until the night before a test to review my lecture notes.	26	17	23	13	15	9	8	7	VT
26. I listen carefully to a lecture, but I do not take notes.	9	28	22	20	9	10	14	6	MLT
27. I take time to review the chapter.	28	27	29	16	1	6	6	7	VT
28. I really "dig in" when I study.	33	30	15	15	7	9	3	7	VT
29. I skip over charts, graphs, and tables when I read a chapter.	14	20	26	14	15	9	14	5	T
30. If I have any time left, I check over my test to avoid errors.	46	24	22	11	3	1	5	7	VT
31. Because I want to remember, I listen carefully to any explanations in class.	57	25	19	8	1	1	1	7	VT
Mode								7	VT

Academic Performance of the Learners

Table 4.3

The academic performance of the learners in the first and second quarter

Teacher	1 st Quarter	2 nd Quarter	Total	Verbal Description
1	84.18	83.92	84.05	Satisfactory
2	84.18	83.92	84.05	Satisfactory
3	81.24	81.35	81.30	Satisfactory
4	83.76	85.02	84.39	Satisfactory
5	83.76	85.02	84.39	Satisfactory
6	85.23	88.53	86.88	Very Satisfactory
7	83.67	84.30	83.99	Satisfactory
8	81.31	84.94	83.13	Satisfactory
9	84.00	82.50	83.25	Satisfactory
10	86.57	88.98	87.78	Very Satisfactory
11	88.00	89.45	88.73	Very Satisfactory

12	85.36	87.52	86.44	Very Satisfactory
13	85.40	86.34	85.87	Very Satisfactory
14	85.40	86.34	85.87	Very Satisfactory
15	84.52	85.63	85.08	Very Satisfactory
16	83.61	82.67	83.14	Satisfactory
17	83.76	83.89	83.83	Satisfactory
18	85.62	86.20	85.91	Very Satisfactory
19	83.49	85.68	84.59	Very Satisfactory
20	84.21	85.14	84.68	Very Satisfactory
21	81.50	83.00	82.25	Satisfactory
22	83.56	84.53	84.05	Satisfactory
23	82.35	83.00	82.68	Satisfactory
24	88.89	89.56	89.23	Very Satisfactory
Grand Mean	84.32	85.31	84.81	Satisfactory

Levels of Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Very Satisfactory	11	45.83
Satisfactory	13	54.17
Total	24	100

V. Relationship Between Teaching Strategies on Students' Motivation, Study Habits and Academic Performance

Table 5

A Statistical table showing the relationship between teaching strategies on study habits, motivation and academic performance

Correlations							
		Strategies	Study Habits	Motivation	Academic Performance	Interpretation	Decision
Strategies	Correlation (r)	1.000	.102	.169	-.079		
	p-value	.	.634	.430	.712		
	N	24	24	24	24		
Study Habits	Correlation (r)	.102	1.000	.098	-.152		
	p-value	.634	.	.649	.479		
	N	24	24	24	24		
Motivation	Correlation (r)	.169	.098	1.000	.140	Not significant	Ho not rejected
	p-value	.430	.649	.	.515		
	N	24	24	24	24		
Academic Performance	Correlation (r)	-.079	-.152	.140	1.000		
	p-value	.712	.479	.515	.		
	N	24	24	24	24		

DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile

The study's demographic analysis of Mathematics teachers revealed a predominantly youthful workforce, with many belonging to the 26-30 age bracket, suggesting fresh perspectives. There is also a notable gender imbalance favouring females, consistent with national trends. Despite youthfulness, many teachers boast over ten years of experience, promising a blend of energy and expertise. However, there is a lack of specialized Mathematics education training among teachers, indicating a need for professional development. While most teachers hold bachelor's degrees, further educational opportunities could enhance their qualifications. The profile underscores strengths and areas for improvement in the mathematics teaching workforce.

Teachers Strategies

The results of this study highlight the diverse range of teaching strategies employed by Mathematics teachers in the division. Collaborative learning emerged as the most frequently utilized remediating strategy, underscoring the value of fostering a cooperative and interactive learning environment. Explicit instruction, differentiated instruction, and repetition were also consistently incorporated, reflecting the teachers' efforts to provide clear explanations, cater to individual learning needs, and reinforce key concepts through practice on developing the least mastered competencies in Mathematics. However, it is noteworthy that game-based instruction and models and manipulatives were employed less frequently. This discrepancy could be attributed to limited resources or a lack of familiarity with these approaches.

Shimazoe and Aldrich (2018) highlight the benefits of cooperative learning, emphasizing its positive impact on deep learning, academic performance, social skills, and critical thinking abilities. Similarly, Jitendra et al. (2015) conducted a randomized controlled trial demonstrating the efficacy of explicit instruction in enhancing students' conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills in mathematics, particularly in proportional reasoning. Furthermore, recent research on differentiated instruction supports its effectiveness in addressing students' diverse learning needs and boosting confidence in fundamental mathematical operations (Ahugayon et al., 2020). Moreover, Heyd-Metzuyanim and Graven (2016) and Kim et al. (2015) emphasize the positive outcomes of peer tutoring, including improved math performance and increased motivation among students, while Hoops et al. (2016) highlight the role of peer tutoring in creating a supportive learning community focused on mastering mathematical concepts.

Students Motivation, Study Habits, and Academic Performance

Based on the students' motivational orientations, it was revealed that most students identified the majority of the indicators as very true of their own characteristics. This suggests a high self-perception alignment among the students regarding their motivational orientations. Students in Math class exhibit a range of positive study habits and attitudes, including consistency, focus, effective strategies, enjoyment of learning,

and a desire for improvement. The students exhibit highly effective and diligent study habits, including structured routines, focused efforts, strategic planning, and systematic practices aimed at academic excellence. The academic performance of the Grade 7 students in the division falls between 80-84 which is a satisfactory level.

Significant Difference between Teachers Profiles and Teacher-Strategies

Educational Attainment with a p-value of 0.022 had a significant difference on academic performance; therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. Other demographic profiles' p-value was greater than 0.05 which indicates no significance; hence the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Significant Relationship Between Students' Motivation, Study Habits and Academic Performance to Teacher Strategies

Teacher strategies have no significant relationship with students' motivation, study habits, and academic performance since the p value is greater than 0.05.

Proposed Intervention Based on the Findings of the Study

Drawing upon the study's findings, a comprehensive Lesson Exemplar was crafted and tailored to enhance the Least Mastered Competencies of Mathematics 7 learners. The researcher integrated the teaching strategies identified in the study, ensuring that the exemplar is connected with the instructional approaches employed by teachers, focusing on addressing learners' specific needs and leveraging effective pedagogical methods. The Lesson Exemplar aimed to foster a deeper understanding and mastery of key mathematical concepts. By aligning closely with teachers' strategies and catering to students' diverse learning styles and preferences, this package endeavored to promote meaningful engagement and facilitate tangible academic progress.

Conclusions

Mathematics teachers in the division primarily employed student-centered teaching strategies, such as collaborative learning, explicit instruction, differentiated instruction, and repetition. These strategies are favoured due to their effectiveness in promoting active learning, catering to diverse learning needs, reinforcing key concepts, and aligning with contemporary pedagogical approaches. Notably, the students exhibited a high self-perception alignment with motivational indicators, suggesting a positive orientation towards their studies.

Furthermore, the students in the Math class demonstrated a range of positive study habits and attitudes, including consistency, focus, effective strategies, enjoyment of learning, and a desire for improvement. These characteristics, coupled with their highly effective and diligent study habits involving structured routines, focused efforts, strategic planning, and systematic practices, contribute to their satisfactory academic performance, with Grade 7 students achieving scores between 80 and 84.

Interestingly, while educational attainment was found to have a significant impact on academic performance, with the null hypothesis being rejected, other demographic factors, such as age, sex, length of service, employment status, and the number of training courses attended, did not exhibit significant differences in the teaching strategies employed by the teachers.

However, the study did not find a significant relationship between teacher strategies and study habits, motivation, and academic performance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This suggests that while student-centered teaching strategies, positive study habits and motivational orientations are essential components of academic success, other factors that may influence the relationship between these variables and academic performance warrant further investigation.

Overall, the findings highlight the importance of employing effective teaching strategies, fostering positive study habits and motivational orientations among students, and considering the influence of demographic factors on academic performance in educational research and practice.

Recommendations

- The profile of the teacher-respondents, specifically the number of training sessions attended, revealed a lack of mathematics-related training among teachers. The administration may provide professional development opportunities and training for teachers to ensure continuous improvement and adoption of effective teaching strategies in Mathematics.
- The remediation strategies of the teachers showed that collaborative learning emerged as the most frequently used remediation strategy. These strategies can enhance student engagement, promote critical thinking, and reinforce mathematical concepts through interactive discussions and problem-solving. The teachers may continue to emphasize and support collaborative learning, explicit instruction, differentiated instruction, and repetition strategies as they align with student-centered pedagogical approaches.
- The findings indicate that teachers less frequently utilized game-based instruction and using models and manipulatives because of a lack of resources. To address this gap, professional development programs or workshops could be organized to equip teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to effectively incorporate these engaging and hands-on strategies into their teaching repertoire.
- To increase students' motivation and study habits, teachers may explore additional active learning strategies and incorporate them into the teaching and learning process.
- The administration may implement initiatives and programs to further foster positive study habits, consistency, focus, and a love for learning among students. Provide guidance and resources to students to help them develop effective study strategies and time management skills.
- Future researchers may conduct further research to investigate other factors influencing students' motivation, study habits, and academic performance.
- To propose lesson exemplars aligned with the teaching strategies and specific

learning competencies in Mathematics that cater to the students' needs and interests.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In conducting this research, the researcher adhered to the highest ethical standards to ensure the integrity of the study and the protection of the participants. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were provided with clear and comprehensive information about the study's purpose, procedures, potential risks, benefits, and their rights. Confidentiality was rigorously maintained by anonymizing data and securely storing all information. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without repercussions. The research design prioritized minimizing any potential harm, and transparency was maintained throughout the process.

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